

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE OF INDUSTRIAL COOPERATION

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ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОЙ КООПЕРАЦИИ

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The article considers models of foreign experience of industrial cooperation, using the example of America, Japan, China and Spain. It should be noted that the world practice of industrial cooperation has a certain position, which effectively affect the economies of their countries. In the course of the study, the problems encountered in Uzbekistan in this activity were analyzed. The following are recommendations for improving industrial cooperation in the country.

Аннотация

В статье рассмотрены модели зарубежного опыта промышленной кооперации, на примере Америки, Японии, Китая и Испании. Необходимо отметить, что мировая практика по промышленной кооперации имеет определённую позицию, которые результативно влияют на экономику своих стран. В ходе исследования проанализированы проблемы, встречающиеся в Узбекистане по данной деятельности. Далее даны рекомендации по улучшению промышленной кооперации в стране.

Keywords: cooperation, industry, model, subcontractor, cluster.

Ключевые слова: кооперация, промышленность, модель, субподрядчик, кластер.

Introduction.

Industrial cooperation is considered by many countries as a tool to achieve high production efficiency through the division of labor, specialization, rational use of existing production and technological capacities and optimization of the use of all types of resources. This model of production organization has become widespread, especially over the past 20 years, and has become one of the significant factors in the high rates of economic development in both developed industrial countries (Japan, USA, EU) and developing countries (India, China, Vietnam, Turkey, etc.).

According to expert estimates, the share of industrial cooperation in the manufacturing industry of developed industrial countries ranges from 25-35%, and in the production of electronic equipment, road construction equipment, aircraft and a number of other types of products reaches 50-70%. According to Nikkei estimates, out of approximately 10 thousand parts that make up a modern car, 9.8 thousand are produced on the basis of industrial cooperation, including cross-country.

Theoretical aspects of research work.

Experts identify the following main benefits that the economy receives from the development of industrial cooperation[1].

1. A significant reduction in the preparation time for the production of new goods and a decrease in their capital intensity. According to the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), interstate agreements on industrial cooperation on average reduce the preparation time for the production of new products by approximately 14-20 months compared to organizing it exclusively on their own, and also reduce the cost of developing a new product by 50-70%.

2. Improving the quality of manufactured industrial products. Industrial cooperation makes it possible to achieve over 90% of the quality level of a foreign partner's products, while the development of foreign technology on its own makes it possible to provide only 70-80% of this indicator.

As Bloomberg notes, in the context of a chronic shortage of funds in developing countries, their participation in industrial cooperation is one of the most effective measures for the technical re-equipment of industry, expanding the export orientation of production, achieving international standards for product quality and increasing employment.

In developed countries, industrial cooperation and, in particular, subcontracting are natural tools for increasing the efficiency of industrial production and ensuring overall economic growth. Subcontracting was one of the components that ensured high rates of economic development in such countries as Japan, the USA, Germany, France, Italy, Spain, and Turkey.

So in Japan, in the early 80s. the share of small firms working under subcontract schemes was 65%, and in the electronics industry (the main branch of the Japanese economy), this figure reached 86%.

Today, more than 350 thousand enterprises are involved in the process of industrial cooperation in the countries of the European Community, which provides jobs for more than 4 million people. The total volume of products manufactured under subcontracts in 1999 exceeded 35 billion euros, which is about 15% of the total volume of products manufactured in the EU countries.

In building cooperation relations, two models are distinguished, which in the literature are called American and Japanese³.

The American model is based on the interaction of a large number of customers and contractors, that is, it requires a developed subcontracting market. The main criterion for selecting contractors is the offered price[2]. Such a system exists in close connection with the developed small business, the innovative activity of contractors, the availability of leasing relations for subcontractors, etc[3]. For the American model, the relationship between the customer and the contractor is built within the framework of one specific order and is not designed for the long term. A wide offer from the performers allows the customer to choose the best option for the execution of his order.

Usually a large automobile manufacturing enterprise has 2-2.5 thousand subcontractors. Such giants of the American automotive industry as Chrysler, Ford and General Motors manufacture a little more than 1/3 of the components themselves. The remaining components are supplied under contract agreements. The development of the American model of industrial cooperation in the sphere of small and medium business was facilitated not only by the liberal economic policy, but also by the system of state orders, in particular for the defense sector.

The Japanese model is characterized by the ranking of subcontractors depending on the available production capacities and the level of technology. In Japan, a multi-level subcontracting system has developed: a contractor submits an order to several subcontractors, who in turn cooperate with lower level subcontractors. A large Japanese automobile manufacturer has an average of 300-400 subcontractors. Direct long-term relationships are established with subcontractors of the first level.

Such giants of the Japanese automotive industry as Nissan and Toyota independently produce a little more than 1/4 of the components used, receiving the rest under subcontract orders. The criteria for selecting subcontractors are, first of all, not prices, but quality, technical compatibility of products, reliability of partners[4]. Typically, the contract is concluded for the period of production of a certain model of the product and is extended in the future if the partner satisfies the customer. As for the price, the Japanese contractors abandoned the idea of knocking it down by organizing a competitive struggle between subcontractors[5]. On the contrary, customers seek to establish strong partnerships with contractors to improve production efficiency. Although the initial price is set on the basis of a detailed cost estimate, it is subsequently added to the share of the economic benefit received by the contractor[6]. The initial price takes into account the profit of the subcontractor, and the depreciation of the equipment used, and the increase in prices for raw materials. A feature of the Japanese model of industrial cooperation is the close industrial and technical integration of large customers and smaller contractors. Often the customer maintains regular contacts with the contractor,

takes an active part in mastering the production of components, assists in improving quality control, and provides technical, technological and financial assistance. The Japanese model of cooperation allows the formation of sectoral and clusters, which is its undoubted advantage over the American model.

Analyzing the two presented models of industrial cooperation, the experts came to the conclusion that the automotive industry in Japan, in comparison with the automotive industry in the United States, has a 300-600-dollar greater gain per car produced (these figures were also confirmed for branches of Japanese companies abroad).

Among specialists, the **experience of China**, one of the leading countries in the development of industrial cooperation, is of great interest. A feature of the industrial policy of Beijing is its so-called. bilateral in nature, when a country simultaneously attracts foreign industrial companies to the country and transfers production facilities abroad [9].

Currently, China is the world's largest producer of more than 220 categories of industrial products, including steel, cement and automobiles, in particular, the country produces 38% of the world's machine tools, 41% of ships and 60% of power generation equipment. At the same time, the number of Chinese-owned companies abroad has increased to over 20,000.

China highlights the following key principles in the development of industrial cooperation with foreign countries.

First, a balanced approach to the interests and principles of their partners. Chinese companies are required to strictly comply with the law when doing business and fulfill their social obligations, incl. when investing abroad.

Second, win-win cooperation, which involves promoting industrial cooperation in a pragmatic and efficient manner, based on equality and mutual benefit.

Third, openness and inclusiveness, according to which China intends to act in strict accordance with market principles, follow accepted international practices, and support companies in independent decision-making and sole responsibility for their own profits and losses[2].

Consider the **experience of Spain** in the development of subcontract relations. Since the mid-70s. 20th century in Spain, which lagged far behind the leading industrial countries in terms of the competitiveness of its industry, the active introduction of industrial cooperation and subcontracting mechanisms began. The initiators of the project were: Chambers of Commerce and Industry, Institute of Small and Medium Enterprises, Institute of Foreign Trade. The main idea was to overcome the economic crisis by loading Spanish industrial enterprises with production orders from large multinational companies (mainly automotive). An important stage in the development of the subcontracting system in Spain was the participation of subcontractor enterprises in monographic specialized exhibitions (Chicago, Copenhagen, Paris, Hanover, Birmingham).

The spread of the practice of subcontracting allowed Spain to quickly develop a network of small and medium-sized enterprises, which initially specialized in fulfilling orders from large foreign companies [7]. The economic recovery and the subsequent deepening of industrial cooperation processes led to the revival of large-scale industry, which made it possible to form an internal subcontracting market.

Analyze and result of research work.

Most of the EAEU countries are traditional foreign trade partners of Uzbekistan. At the end of 2020, they accounted for more than 30% of the country's trade turnover: among Uzbekistan's foreign trade partners, Russia ranks second with a trade turnover of \$5.6 billion, Kazakhstan is third (\$3.01 billion), Kyrgyzstan is seventh (\$903 million), Belarus is the twentieth (280.1 million dollars) [10].

At the same time, in Uzbekistan, the EAEU countries account for 32% of the total number of enterprises with the participation of foreign capital - the number of operating enterprises with the participation of the capital of the business circles of the Russian Federation amounted to 1,934 units, Kazakhstan - 902 units, Kyrgyzstan - 161 units, Belarus - 80 units, Armenia - 36 units.

It is also necessary to take into account the fact that the developed and actively developing sectors of the Uzbek economy are included in the list of priority industrial sectors of the EAEU. In particular, these are the automotive industry, light, chemical and petrochemical industries, the production of machinery and equipment for agriculture and forestry, plastic and rubber products, household appliances, etc. [11].

It is worth emphasizing that over the past few years, Uzbekistan has paid special attention to industrial development with the parallel promotion of a policy to reduce raw material exports and diversify the production of high value-added products. For example, by 2025 it is planned to stop the supply of natural gas abroad.

Based on the fact that the development of industrial production with high added value is facing fierce competition in the world market, it became necessary to create a separate platform for discussing and developing new joint ideas and projects in the field of industrial cooperation between Uzbekistan and the EAEU countries.

In the long term, such cooperation will open up new opportunities for the Uzbek side and the countries of the Union to expand interregional production chains, achieve international product quality standards, form new export-oriented production, and implement the most efficient utilization of production capacities.

Ultimately, industrial cooperation between Uzbekistan and the EAEU member states will significantly increase the competitiveness of industrial enterprises by expanding the volume and range of production of high value-added goods, as well as improving quality and minimizing production costs.

Conclusion.

An analysis of our research shows that the following measures are proposed for the development of industrial cooperation:

1. Improving the legal framework governing industrial cooperation. A modern legal framework that meets international requirements is an important factor in the development of industrial cooperation and, when developing it, calls for paying attention to: first, a clear regulation of relations between the cooperating parties; secondly, the creation of state structures involved in the direct development of industrial cooperation, including within the country; thirdly, to provide for various measures to stimulate and support the subjects of industrial cooperation.

2. Improving the business environment, including in particular:

a) accelerating the privatization of state assets in order to stimulate the inflow of foreign capital and technology into industry;

b) optimization of tax and customs tariff regulation in the industrial sector;

c) reducing administrative barriers and ensuring the required quality of law enforcement practice, etc.

3. Stimulation of national companies to organize industrial production in foreign countries.

References

1. В.Е.Егоров, "Мировой опыт развития кооперации в сельском хозяйстве," pp. 184–189, 2012.
2. Р. Р. Исламиев, "Основные направления развития кооперации и интеграции в аграрном производстве," vol. 4, no. 96, pp. 75–77, 2012.
3. Matchanova, "Formation and development of cooperation of agro-industrial complex in the conditions of modernization economics of the Republic of Karakalpakstan," *Austrian J. Humanit. Soc. Sci.*, pp. 11–14, 2015, doi: 10.20534/ajh-15-3.4-11-14.
4. UNCTAD, "Science, technology and innovation for enterprise development," vol. 15836, no. September, 2018, [Online]. Available: https://unctad.org/meetings/en/SessionalDocuments/ciid39_en.pdf.
5. А. В. Меликян and Б. В. Железов, "Инновационная деятельность международных сотрудников российского вуза (на примере НИУ ВШЭ)," vol. 1, no. 40, pp. 274–286, 2013.
6. Ж.Ю.Уланова, "Формирование системы финансового контроллинга на предприятии," 2016.
7. Ш. М. Муродов, "Формирование и развитие сельскохозяйственной кооперации в плодово-овощном подкомплексе АПК Узбекистана," pp. 431–438, 2016.
8. <https://xn--90abkhe5acaqlhe.xn--p1ai/pages/mirovoy-opyt-promyshlennoy-kooperatsii-v-malom-i-srednem-biznese>
9. <https://invest.gov.uz/ru/mediacenter/news/privatization-effectiveness-considered/>
10. <https://www.agro.uz/ru/agroklasterlar-va-kooperatsiyalar/#1640501149812-d8f405e5-8eb3>